

Tunable metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor based on doped semiconductor nanocrystals

Francesco Scotognella

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

e-mail address: francesco.scotognella@polito.it

Abstract

Electroluminescence of metal halide perovskites has been widely reported via the fabrication and optimization of light emitting diodes and light emitting transistors. Light emitting transistors are particularly interesting owing to the additional control of the gate voltage on the electroluminescence. In this work, the design of a microcavity, with a defect mode that can be tuned with an applied voltage, integrated with a metal halide light emitting transistor is shown. The optical properties of the device have been simulated with the transfer matrix method, considering the wavelength dependent refractive indexes of all the employed materials. The tunability of the microcavity has been obtained via the employment of doped semiconductor nanocrystalline films, which show a tunable plasma frequency and, thus, a tunable refractive index as a function of the applied voltage. Consequently, the tunability of the electroluminescence of the metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor has been demonstrated.

Keywords: light emitting transistors; metal halide perovskites; microcavities.

Introduction

The electroluminescence of metal halide perovskites is attracting increasing attention owing to the narrowband emission, near-unity photoluminescence efficiency, and low-cost solution-based fabrication [1]. In addition to the manufacture of very efficient solar cells [2–6] and light-emitting diodes [7–9], the development of perovskite-based light-emitting transistors is of great interest [10–12].

To enhance the electroluminescence of light emitting transistors, the integration of photonic crystals as gate dielectrics has been reported in organic light emitting transistors. In this way, enhanced emission efficiency and enhanced emission directionality has been demonstrated [13,14]. Because of the similar wet chemistry fabrication techniques for organic semiconductors and metal halide perovskites, the photonic crystal as gate dielectric can be implemented also for metal halide perovskite light emitting transistors. To further increase the enhancement, the combination of a metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor with a microcavity has been proposed, in which a photonic crystal is used as gate dielectric and the other photonic crystal is fabricated onto the metal halide perovskite layer [15].

With a proper choice of materials, a microcavity can be tuned with an external stimulus in order to tune the light emitting transistor emission. For example, the employment of metals or doped semiconductors [16,17] as components of the photonic crystal leads to a tunable photonic band gap with the application of an external voltage [18]. In this work, the design of a metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor combined with a microcavity, which can be tuned with an external voltage, is presented. The transmission spectra are simulated with the transfer matrix method and wavelength dependent refractive indexes of all the materials have been employed.

Methods

The simulations of the light transmission spectra of the structures studied in this work have been performed with the transfer matrix method, which is well established for one-dimensional multilayer systems [19–21]. The studied system is glass/multilayer/air.

For silicon dioxide (SiO₂), the following Sellmeier equation has been employed [22,23]

$$n_{SiO_2}^2(\lambda) - 1 = \frac{0.6961663\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.0684043^2} + \frac{0.4079426\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.1162414^2} + \frac{0.8974794\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 9.896161^2} \quad (1)$$

For titanium dioxide (TiO₂), the wavelength-dependent refractive index is given by [24]

$$n_{TiO_2}(\lambda) = \left(4.99 + \frac{1}{96.6\lambda^{1.1}} + \frac{1}{4.60\lambda^{1.95}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

The wavelength dependent refractive of the active material MAPbI₃ is taken from Refs. [25,26]. The optical response of indium tin oxide (ITO) nanocrystalline films and fluorine indium co-doped cadmium oxide (FICO) nanocrystalline films has been simulated by employing the Drude model and the effective medium approximation [27]. The filling factor of the ITO and FICO nanocrystalline films is 0.65. For ITO $N = 2.49 \times 10^{26} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\varepsilon_\infty = 4$, $m^* = 0.4m_e$ and $\Gamma = 0.1132 \text{ eV}$ [28]. For FICO $N = 1.68 \times 10^{27} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\varepsilon_\infty = 5.6$, $m^* = 0.43m_e$ and $\Gamma = 0.07 \text{ eV}$ [28,29].

Results and Discussion

In Figure 1 the sketch the MAPbI₃ metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor coupled with a microcavity is shown. The thickness of the MAPbI₃ layer is 40 nm, the thickness of the ITO layers is 100 nm, the thickness of the FICO nanocrystalline layers is 112.7 nm, the thickness of the SiO₂ layers is 144.15 nm, and the thickness of TiO₂ layers is 73.5 nm.

The photonic crystal below the MAPbI₃ layer, made by TiO₂ and FICO nanocrystals, functions as a gate dielectric. Instead, the photonic crystal above the MAPbI₃ layer is made by TiO₂ and FICO nanoparticle layers sandwiched between two transparent electrodes of ITO and functions as electro-optic switch.

Figure 1. Sketch of the light emitting transistor integrated with a microcavity in which the upper photonic crystal is a tunable switch activated by an external voltage.

The application of an external voltage between the two ITO electrodes leads to a change of the carrier density of the doped semiconductor nanocrystals, i.e., FICO nanocrystals, resulting in a change of the dielectric function of the FICO nanoparticle layers and, thus, to a change of the effective refractive index of the photonic crystal. Such effective refractive index change gives rise to a shift of the photonic band gap of the photonic crystal [18,30]. Referring to the structure sketched in Figure 1, the shift of the photonic band gap of the photonic crystal above the MAPbI₃ layer results in a modification of the light transmission spectrum of the light emitting transistor coupled with the microcavity. In Figure 2 the transmission spectrum of the light emitting transistor coupled with the microcavity is shown for two different carrier densities of the FICO nanocrystals: Solid black curve corresponds to the structure with FICO carrier density of 1.68×10^{27} charges/m³, while dotted-dashed red curve corresponds to FICO carrier density of 3.68×10^{27} charges/m³.

Figure 2. Transmission spectrum of the light emitting transistor coupled with a tunable microcavity (structure depicted in Figure 1). Solid black curve corresponds to the structure with FICO carrier density of 1.68×10^{27} charges/m³, while dotted-dashed red curve corresponds to FICO carrier density of 3.68×10^{27} charges/m³.

With such change of carrier density of FICO nanocrystals, it is possible to suppress almost completely the defect mode of the microcavity. This is mainly due to the asymmetry generated between the two photonic crystals of the microcavities, i.e., the one below the MAPbI₃ layer and the one above the MAPbI₃ layer. To highlight the possibility to tune the defect mode of the microcavity, in Figure 3 the transmission spectrum of the light emitting transistor coupled with the microcavity is shown for six different carrier densities of the FICO nanocrystals: 1.68×10^{27} charges/m³ (solid black curve), 1.88×10^{27} charges/m³ (dotted-dashed red curve), 2.08×10^{27} charges/m³ (dashed dark red curve), 2.28×10^{27} charges/m³ (solid brown curve), 2.48×10^{27} charges/m³ (dotted-dashed dark green curve), 2.68×10^{27} charges/m³ (dashed green curve). The arrow highlights the increase of carrier density.

Figure 3. Transmission spectrum of light emitting transistor coupled with a tunable microcavity (structure depicted in Figure 1), in the spectral region of the defect mode, for FICO carrier density of 1.68×10^{27} charges/m³ (solid black curve), 1.88×10^{27} charges/m³ (dotted-dashed red curve), 2.08×10^{27} charges/m³ (dashed dark red curve), 2.28×10^{27} charges/m³ (solid brown curve), 2.48×10^{27} charges/m³ (dotted-dashed dark green curve), 2.68×10^{27} charges/m³ (dashed green curve).

A shift of about 20 nm is shown. With a simple linear fit, it is possible to determine that 7.2×10^{25} charges/m³ are needed for a shift of 1 nm of the defect mode. In a similar photonic structure, i.e., a photonic crystal made with indium tin oxide and titanium dioxide layers, a shift of 23 nm has been achieved with an external voltage of 10 V [30]. Considering the electroluminescence (EL) of a light emitting transistor based on MAPbI₃ (the experimental data are taken from Ref. [11]), it is possible to finely tune the EL by changing the FICO nanocrystal carrier density (Figure 4). As in Figure 3, the arrow underlines the increase of carrier density.

Figure 4. Electroluminescence (EL) of the metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor / microcavity for FICO carrier density of 1.68×10^{27} charges/m³ (solid black curve), 1.88×10^{27} charges/m³ (dotted-dashed red curve), 2.08×10^{27} charges/m³ (dashed dark red curve), 2.28×10^{27} charges/m³ (solid brown curve), 2.48×10^{27} charges/m³ (dotted-dashed dark green curve), 2.68×10^{27} charges/m³ (dashed green curve).

Conclusion

In this work the tunability, via the application of an external voltage, of the defect mode of the microcavity combined with a metal halide perovskite light emitting transistor has been studied. In this way, the electroluminescence of metal halide perovskite active layer can be thus modulated with the electric field. This tunability can be very interesting for lighting applications with tunable electrically stimulated light emitters. Since the integration of a microcavity in a light emitting transistor can lead to a possible electrically injected metal halide perovskite laser, the device presented in this work can be interesting also for the realization of tunable lasers.

Acknowledgements

I acknowledge the Research and Innovation Staff Exchange program SONAR (Marie Curie Actions) of the European Union's Horizon 2020 [Grant number 734690]. This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. [816313]).

References

- [1] A. Liu, C. Bi, R. Guo, M. Zhang, X. Qu, J. Tian, Electroluminescence Principle and Performance Improvement of Metal Halide Perovskite Light-Emitting Diodes, *Advanced Optical Materials*. 9 (2021) 2002167. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adom.202002167>.
- [2] G.-W. Kim, A. Petrozza, Defect Tolerance and Intolerance in Metal-Halide Perovskites, *Advanced Energy Materials*. 10 (2020) 2001959. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202001959>.
- [3] J.Y. Kim, J.-W. Lee, H.S. Jung, H. Shin, N.-G. Park, High-Efficiency Perovskite Solar Cells, *Chem. Rev.* 120 (2020) 7867–7918. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.0c00107>.
- [4] M. Jeong, I.W. Choi, E.M. Go, Y. Cho, M. Kim, B. Lee, S. Jeong, Y. Jo, H.W. Choi, J. Lee, J.-H. Bae, S.K. Kwak, D.S. Kim, C. Yang, Stable perovskite solar cells with efficiency exceeding 24.8% and 0.3-V voltage loss, *Science*. 369 (2020) 1615–1620. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abb7167>.
- [5] X. Wu, B. Li, Z. Zhu, C.-C. Chueh, A.K.-Y. Jen, Designs from single junctions, heterojunctions to multijunctions for high-performance perovskite solar cells, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 50 (2021) 13090–13128. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1CS00841B>.
- [6] T.J. Jacobsson, A. Hultqvist, A. García-Fernández, A. Anand, A. Al-Ashouri, A. Hagfeldt, A. Crovetto, A. Abate, A.G. Ricciardulli, A. Vijayan, A. Kulkarni, A.Y. Anderson, B.P. Darwich, B. Yang, B.L. Coles, C.A.R. Perini, C. Rehermann, D. Ramirez, D. Fairen-Jimenez, D. Di Girolamo, D. Jia, E. Avila, E.J. Juarez-Perez, F. Baumann, F. Mathies, G.S.A. González, G. Boschloo, G. Nasti, G. Paramasivam, G. Martínez-Denegri, H. Näsström, H. Michaels, H. Köbler, H. Wu, I. Benesperi, M.I. Dar, I. Bayrak Pehlivan, I.E. Gould, J.N. Vagott, J. Dagar, J. Kettle, J. Yang, J. Li, J.A. Smith, J. Pascual, J.J. Jerónimo-Rendón, J.F. Montoya, J.-P. Correa-Baena, J. Qiu, J. Wang, K. Sveinbjörnsson, K. Hirselandt, K. Dey, K. Frohna, L. Mathies, L.A. Castriotta, M.H. Aldamasy, M. Vasquez-Montoya, M.A. Ruiz-Preciado, M.A. Flatken, M.V. Khenkin, M. Grischek, M. Kedia, M. Saliba, M. Anaya, M. Veldhoen, N. Arora, O. Shargaieva, O. Maus, O.S. Game, O. Yudilevich, P. Fassel, Q. Zhou, R. Betancur, R. Munir, R. Patidar, S.D. Stranks, S. Alam, S. Kar, T. Unold, T. Abzieher, T. Edvinsson, T.W. David, U.W. Paetzold, W. Zia, W. Fu, W. Zuo, V.R.F. Schröder, W. Tress, X. Zhang, Y.-H. Chiang, Z. Iqbal, Z. Xie, E. Unger, An open-access database and analysis tool for perovskite solar cells based on the FAIR data principles, *Nat Energy*. 7 (2022) 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00941-3>.
- [7] A. Fakharuddin, M.K. Gangishetty, M. Abdi-Jalebi, S.-H. Chin, A.R. bin Mohd Yusoff, D.N. Congreve, W. Tress, F. Deschler, M. Vasilopoulou, H.J. Bolink, Perovskite light-emitting diodes, *Nat Electron*. 5 (2022) 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-022-00745-7>.
- [8] H. Li, H. Lin, D. Ouyang, C. Yao, C. Li, J. Sun, Y. Song, Y. Wang, Y. Yan, Y. Wang, Q. Dong, W.C.H. Choy, Efficient and Stable Red Perovskite Light-Emitting Diodes with Operational Stability >300 h, *Advanced Materials*. 33 (2021) 2008820. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202008820>.
- [9] B. Guo, R. Lai, S. Jiang, L. Zhou, Z. Ren, Y. Lian, P. Li, X. Cao, S. Xing, Y. Wang, W. Li, C. Zou, M. Chen, Z. Hong, C. Li, B. Zhao, D. Di, Ultrastable near-infrared perovskite light-emitting diodes, *Nat. Photon*. 16 (2022) 637–643. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41566-022-01046-3>.
- [10] X.Y. Chin, D. Cortecchia, J. Yin, A. Bruno, C. Soci, Lead iodide perovskite light-emitting field-effect transistor, *Nature Communications*. 6 (2015) 7383. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8383>.
- [11] F. Maddalena, X.Y. Chin, D. Cortecchia, A. Bruno, C. Soci, Brightness Enhancement in Pulsed-Operated Perovskite Light-Emitting Transistors, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*. 10 (2018) 37316–37325. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b11057>.
- [12] M. Klein, J. Li, A. Bruno, C. Soci, Co-Evaporated Perovskite Light-Emitting Transistor Operating at Room Temperature, *Advanced Electronic Materials*. 7 (2021) 2100403. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aelm.202100403>.

- [13] E.B. Namdas, B.B.Y. Hsu, J.D. Yuen, I.D.W. Samuel, A.J. Heeger, Optoelectronic Gate Dielectrics for High Brightness and High-Efficiency Light-Emitting Transistors, *Advanced Materials*. 23 (2011) 2353–2356. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201004102>.
- [14] M. Natali, S.D. Quiroga, L. Passoni, L. Criante, E. Benvenuti, G. Bolognini, L. Favaretto, M. Melucci, M. Muccini, F. Scotognella, F.D. Fonzo, S. Toffanin, Simultaneous Tenfold Brightness Enhancement and Emitted-Light Spectral Tunability in Transparent Ambipolar Organic Light-Emitting Transistor by Integration of High-k Photonic Crystal, *Advanced Functional Materials*. 27 (2017) 1605164. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201605164>.
- [15] F. Scotognella, Microcavities integrated in metal halide perovskite light-emitting field-effect transistors, *Results in Physics*. (2022) 106168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2022.106168>.
- [16] A. Agrawal, R.W. Johns, D.J. Milliron, Control of Localized Surface Plasmon Resonances in Metal Oxide Nanocrystals, *Annual Review of Materials Research*. 47 (2017) 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-matsci-070616-124259>.
- [17] I. Kriegel, F. Scotognella, L. Manna, Plasmonic doped semiconductor nanocrystals: Properties, fabrication, applications and perspectives, *Physics Reports*. 674 (2017) 1–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2017.01.003>.
- [18] G.M. Paternò, L. Moscardi, I. Kriegel, F. Scotognella, G. Lanzani, Electro-optic and magneto-optic photonic devices based on multilayer photonic structures, *Journal of Photonics for Energy*. 8 (2018) 1. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JPE.8.032201>.
- [19] M. Born, E. Wolf, A.B. Bhatia, P.C. Clemmow, D. Gabor, A.R. Stokes, A.M. Taylor, P.A. Wayman, W.L. Wilcock, *Principles of Optics: Electromagnetic Theory of Propagation, Interference and Diffraction of Light*, 7th ed., Cambridge University Press, 1999. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139644181>.
- [20] X. Xiao, W. Wenjun, L. Shuhong, Z. Wanquan, Z. Dong, D. Qianqian, G. Xuexi, Z. Bingyuan, Investigation of defect modes with Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ in one-dimensional photonic crystals, *Optik*. 127 (2016) 135–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2015.10.005>.
- [21] P. Lova, G. Manfredi, D. Comoretto, Advances in Functional Solution Processed Planar 1D Photonic Crystals, *Advanced Optical Materials*. 6 (2018) 1800730. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adom.201800730>.
- [22] I.H. Malitson, Interspecimen Comparison of the Refractive Index of Fused Silica*,†, *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, JOSA. 55 (1965) 1205–1209. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSA.55.001205>.
- [23] RefractiveIndex.INFO - Refractive index database, (n.d.). <https://refractiveindex.info/> (accessed November 15, 2019).
- [24] F. Scotognella, A. Chiasera, L. Criante, E. Aluicio-Sarduy, S. Varas, S. Pelli, A. Łukowiak, G.C. Righini, R. Ramponi, M. Ferrari, Metal oxide one dimensional photonic crystals made by RF sputtering and spin coating, *Ceramics International*. 41 (2015) 8655–8659. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2015.03.077>.
- [25] L.J. Phillips, A.M. Rashed, R.E. Treharne, J. Kay, P. Yates, I.Z. Mitrovic, A. Weerakkody, S. Hall, K. Durose, Dispersion relation data for methylammonium lead triiodide perovskite deposited on a (100) silicon wafer using a two-step vapour-phase reaction process, *Data in Brief*. 5 (2015) 926–928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2015.10.026>.
- [26] L.J. Phillips, A.M. Rashed, R.E. Treharne, J. Kay, P. Yates, I.Z. Mitrovic, A. Weerakkody, S. Hall, K. Durose, Maximizing the optical performance of planar CH₃NH₃PbI₃ hybrid perovskite heterojunction stacks, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*. 147 (2016) 327–333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2015.10.007>.
- [27] G.M. Paternò, C. Iseppon, A. D’Altri, C. Fasanotti, G. Merati, M. Randi, A. Desii, E.A.A. Pogna, D. Viola, G. Cerullo, F. Scotognella, I. Kriegel, Solution processable and optically

switchable 1D photonic structures, *Scientific Reports*. 8 (2018) 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-21824-w>.

- [28] I. Kriegel, F. Scotognella, L. Manna, Plasmonic doped semiconductor nanocrystals: Properties, fabrication, applications and perspectives, *Physics Reports*. 674 (2017) 1–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2017.01.003>.
- [29] I. Kriegel, C. Urso, D. Viola, L. De Trizio, F. Scotognella, G. Cerullo, L. Manna, Ultrafast Photodoping and Plasmon Dynamics in Fluorine–Indium Codoped Cadmium Oxide Nanocrystals for All-Optical Signal Manipulation at Optical Communication Wavelengths, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters*. 7 (2016) 3873–3881.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.6b01904>.
- [30] L. Moscardi, G.M. Paternò, A. Chiasera, R. Sorrentino, F. Marangi, I. Kriegel, G. Lanzani, F. Scotognella, Electro-responsivity in electrolyte-free and solution processed Bragg stacks, *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*. (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TC02437F>.